

Solutions for the Yang-Mills-Problem, the Riemann-Guess and the Complexity-Problem (NP = P?) by Isabelle Nekrumi and Esther Nekrumi

1. Solution for the Yang-Mills-Problem:

A Yang-Mills-Theory of Quants:

That means that you have to explain how particles in the sub-atomic world reach the point of eternal stability, which lets them - for example - reach speed of light although having mass.

The answer is, to get infinite stability there has to be a fusion between movement- particles (up-quark and down-quark) and light-particles (electron) together with transport-particles (neutrino). This fusion of movement, light and transport has got the strength to confuse Time-space, to make it weaker, to open time-space and so time-space has to give energy free, which particles can use to become infinite stable. The energy-field, which is opened up by the fusion of movement-, light- and transport-particles do we call the Higgs-field. So, when a particle-fusion out of movement-, light- and transport-particles uses this Higgs-field the energy of the Higgs-field makes the particles infinite stable. They get energy from the Higgs-field, which is as high as infinity. A small part of this never-ending energy shows as mass of the particles, but where is the much, much bigger part of the energy? The much, much bigger part of the never ending energy inside of the particle is shown as super-capabilities inside of the particles. The energy does not go into space it goes right into the user, which is the particle. This is what we see, but we didn't realize this until now. Now we know where the energy goes to and nobody needs a renormalization anymore.

The super-capabilities of the particles are: Bi-location, superposition, invincibility, eternity (a nearly never ending life-span) and speed of light, which is the fundamental problem of the Yang-Mills-problem. The fundamental problem of the Yang-Mills-problem is the question why particles can reach light-speed, with having mass, which is normally impossible (special relativity theory). The particles have energy for super-capabilities, that's why it becomes possible. Now we do not need any longer a renormalization, because we know now how the particles get all the energy that the particles have. They get the energy from the Higgs-field, which was opened up by the

mixture of movement-, light- and transport-particles. Movement, light and transport are something, that time-space do not like, because time-space becomes weaker when time-space reacts with movement, light and transport. Becoming weaker means that time-space has to give energy free. And this energy goes right into particles to make them infinite stable.

These super-capabilities of particles show also in the next higher and bigger dimension inside of the atomic particles in the atomic world. Now we are in the atomic world and not in the sub-atomic world. This context from sub-atomic world to atomic world is called compact simple lie group, which is infinite stability from sub-atomic world into atomic world. This context (compact simple lie group) is not working between atomic world and our world macro (the world in which we exist), because of decoherence. But human beings can copy this fusion of strengths in the world macro. So human beings can also become infinite stable. When we (mankind) would become infinite stable, we would not be addicted to the resources of our planet anymore and the planet would be safe and would survive.

The intrinsic value of particles in the sub-atomic world is "infinite stable". That brings us to the "the self-adjoint operator". The self-adjoint operator is nothing more and nothing less than a sub-atomic particle, which owns a very high quantum of energy, taken from the Higgs-field. The quantum of energy of the particle is infinite. I explained how that works. It's a fusion of strengths which attack time-space and time-space must give energy free. On one side this energy shows in form of mass, but on the other side the biggest quantum of energy of the particle shows not as mass, it shows as super-capabilities inside of the particle that makes the particle become infinite stable, so the self-adjoint operator is a one which is infinite stable. The self-adjoint operator needs to have such a high intrinsic value. If not it would not be a self-adjoint operator. Self-adjoint means doing things with the own power. So this power has to be very high and when something is infinite stable, it has this power. With this power a particle can do what it wants. That's why particles can reach speed of light, with having mass. Only when they are so extremely stable they can reach speed of light with having mass,

which is without being infinite stable not possible, because of the special relativity theory.

2. That brings us to the solution for the Riemann-Guess: To solve the Riemann-Guess you need something which is similar to infinity. What is similar to infinity? It is eternity. Now that we have “infinite stable” as the intrinsic value for sub-atomic particles in the world of quants, we can transfer this intrinsic value to the prim-numbers and then we can transfer the prim-numbers to the real zeros of the XI-function. Then we have a critical straight with an existence-count of 0.5 (1/2), but with the intrinsic energy-value of “infinite stable”, which makes out of the critical straight an existence straight. The number “0.5 (1/2) infinite stable” is the two-dimensional number that Riemann looked for, it’s a complex number. How many non-trivial zeros exist offside of the existence straight? No non-trivial zeros exist offside the existence straight, because nothing can exist when it is offside of the existence straight. Existence only exists on the existence straight that’s why you never find non-trivial zeros offside of the critical straight, which is an existence straight now. When you find non-trivial zeros offside the existence straight, they wouldn’t exist for a long time. They would be there for a short while but then they would vanish again immediately. The first number (0.5) of the number for example $0.5 + 14i$ is always on the critical straight, which is now an existence straight.
3. That brings us to the complexity-problem: Is $NP = P$? What happens when a Higgs-Field is created in the world macro? When a Higgs-Field is created in the world macro, the user will become “infinite stable”, which means that the user would be fitted with super-capabilities. With these super-capabilities it would be possible for the user to solve any problem in an acceptable time. When the user owns super-capabilities, like bi-location, a very large life-span, being invincible, moving in light-speed, then $NP = P$. Another question: Does the user still have any complex problem, when the user owns super-capabilities? I think no. Because with having super-capabilities problems change. Which problems would be still important? Not many. Maybe the stability-problems of our sun or our planet? How can a human being in our world macro become a user and achieve these super-capabilities? Answer: When the human being

builds a reference system. As we remember: To achieve stability in themselves, particles in the world macro build a fusion out of movement, light and transport. So a human being has to copy that and find some of the right components which act confusing against time-space. When these components act confusing against time-space, then the time-space will be no absolute constant in this universe anymore (general theory of relativity) and time-space becomes weaker and has to open up, so energy escapes out of time-space and can be taken by the user of the fusion of components, which is the reference system and so the user becomes also infinite stable like particles in the sub-atomic world.

Which components are useful for a human being to build a reference system? Here a few examples: 1. Counter-rotating movement. 2. Speed which varies. 3. Curved space (that simulates gravity). 4. Signals of light. 5. The observer himself (the observer influences the system). These are things that act confusing to time-space when they are together in a reference system. We saw this inside of the general relativity theory. Stars reach the point of being very stable by using a fusion out of movement, light and gravity, so they create their own super-capability, which is having a very large life-span. For a “powerless” creature like a human being it is probably necessary to use 5 or even more components to create a reference-system which confuses time-space enough, for to open that Higgs-Field that gives energy free, which goes over to the user (the human being). It sounds complicating, but I think it could work easy. When the user is “infinite stable” any problem can be solved in an acceptable short time. This whole thing I call “Infinite-Stable-Mathematics”.

The formula is:

$$t = e$$

which means:

$$\text{time-space} = \text{energy}$$

which means:

Energy is the thing that time-space has to give free, when a user uses the right reference system out of the right extreme strengths.

How can a user find these correct extreme strengths to make out of them an effective reference system? The general relativity theory shows that normal things like movement, light-signals and an observer already have an effect on time-space and make that time is no absolute constant anymore, which means that time-space is no longer almighty in that moment in which the reference system is active. All you need now is a reference system that makes that this moment becomes longer. When the moment becomes longer, time-space can no longer resist and finally has to open up and give free energy to the user of the reference system. The reference system is a mixture out of movement, light-signals, speed, curved space, impulse and the observer (the user). These normal things become altogether in a reference system extreme strengths, because they act in a very confusing way to time-space and time-space must give energy free, which goes straight into the user. The result is that the user is infinite stable, like particles in the sub-atomic world are.

So Greta Thunberg can go to school again. The Planet and mankind will be safe when mankind builds a reference system that makes time-space weaker to become infinite stable.

Isabelle Nekrumi and Esther Nekrumi wish mankind good luck in finding the right reference systems in experiments.